

Creative Bioarray

A Division of Creative Dynamics Inc

A microscopic image of a cell, likely a yeast or similar organism, showing a prominent blue-stained nucleus. The image is partially obscured by a teal diagonal overlay on the right side. A small white arrow points from the cell towards the text.

CELL CYCLE AND CELL CYCLE ASSAY

What is cell cycle?

The Cell Cycle:

Interphase

The Cell Cycle:

Mitosis Prophase

The nuclear envelope begins to break down.
DNA further the condenses into chromosomes.

The Cell Cycle:

Mitosis Metaphase

Chromosomes (composed of sister chromatids) move towards the center of the cell.

The Cell Cycle:

Mitosis Anaphase

The chromosomes rapidly move away from the middle of the cell as the microtubules shorten, pulling the sister chromatids apart and toward opposite poles.

The Cell Cycle:

Mitosis Telophase

The nuclear membrane begins to reappear around each new set of chromosomes, the chromosomes begin to diffuse again, and the spindle apparatus breaks down.

Cell Cycle Assay Principle

Cell Cycle Assay Workflow

Cell Harvest

Wash With
PBS

Cell Fixation

Wash With
PBS

Treat With RNase

Treat With PI/BrdU

Flow Cytometry Analysis

Applications

- By combining genetic manipulations with cell cycle analysis, scientists study roles of specific proteins in cell cycle progression.
- Using cell cycle analysis, scientists can compare progression kinetics.
- Can be used in in vivo cell cycle analysis, BrdU can be injected in rodents and the target cell population can be isolated for cell cycle analysis.

Advantages

- Different type of cell samples we can handle: Fixed, permeabilized, and for live/dead discrimination in intact cells, Live proliferating cells, Treated tissues.

- Fast turnaround time
- Suitable analysis protocol based on different cases
- Reliable results

Thank you!

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